

Metal Chelate Complexes of the Schiff Base Derived from Salicylaldehyde and Ethanolamine

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Some transition metal chelates of the Schiff base, N-hydroxy-ethylsalicylideneimine have been isolated and characterised. The structures of these complexes have been discussed on the basis of their elemental analyses, magnetic moment values, conductivities, electronic and infrared spectral data.

Although metal complexes of Schiff bases of the type (I) derived from salicylaldehyde and various N-alkylamines have been the subject of intensive research¹, those of the ligands in which the amino groups are attached to hydroxyalkyl groups have received relatively little attention. Early in 1964 Calvin and Barkeley², however, studied the oxygen-carrying properties of Cu(II) complex of (I),

FIG (I)

where $R = (CH_2)_2OH$ and $X = H$, but no detailed studies about its structure and other properties appear to have been made. A brief mention of the catalytic activity of Ni(II) complex of (I), where $R = (CH_2)_2OH$ and $X \doteq H$ has also been made³. Kudryavtseva and Savich⁴ reported the preparation of Mo(VI) O_2 complex, where $R = (CH_2)_2OH$ and $X = 5,6$ -benzo.

It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the metallic chelates of the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and hydroxyalkylamines (*i.e.*, amino-alcohols) and to start with, we took up the Schiff base, hydroxyethyl salicylideneimine. But since we started our work, the nickel(II) complex of the ligand was reported by Yamada *et al.*⁵ along with other nickel (II) complexes of this type of ligands^{5,6}, and the titanium (IV) complex by Tandon and Coworker⁷.

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3. G. N. Schranzer, *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. internat. edn.*, 1964, **3**, 185.
4. A. S. Kudryavtsev and I. A. Savich, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1963, **33**, 3763.
5. S. Yamada, *et al.*, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1967, **40**, 1864.
6. R. H. Holm, *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 26.
7. P. Prashar and J. P. Tandon, *J. Less. Common. Metals*, 1967, **13**, 541.

The Schiff base, *N*-hydroxy ethyl salicylideneimine was found by the above workers to act as tridentate ligand with Ni(II) and Ti(IV) ions. In the case of Ni(II) complex, the alcoholic hydroxyl group of the ligand was presumed to coordinate through its oxygen atom giving rise to Ni-OH bond⁵, whereas in Ti(IV) complex, the authors contended that the ligand functioned as a di-anion through replacement of H-atom of the alcoholic OH group⁷. The present communication describes the results of the investigations on the complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(III), Mn(II), V(IV)O, Fe(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II) and U(VI)O₂ with *N*-hydroxyethylsalideneimine (*i.e.*, I, where R = (CH₂)₂OH and X = H).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of N-hydroxyethylsalicylideneimine: This Schiff base was prepared by refluxing a mixture of salicylaldehyde (30.5 g.) and ethanolamine (15.3 g.) in 100 ml. of dry benzene on water-bath for 3 hrs in an apparatus provided with water-separator. After the reflux, the excess benzene was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure. Fraction between 138–140° at 1.0 mm. pressure was collected. The compound forms deep yellow viscous liquid, insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents. Found: N, 8.49%. Calcd. for [C₈H₄(OH)CH = N(CH₂)₂OH]: N, 8.48%.

Preparation of the Metal Complexes: The metallic complexes were prepared by refluxing (2–3 hrs.) requisite amounts of the Schiff base and the corresponding metal acetates (or chlorides in the case of iron, palladium and vanadium) in alcoholic medium. After reflux, the reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate, on standing, deposited well-defined, beautiful crystalline compounds with characteristic colour. When metal chlorides were used, a calculated amount of an ethanol solution of sodium acetate was added to neutralise the hydrochloric acid which was liberated in the solution during complexation. The compounds were recrystallized from ethanol wherever possible.

All the metallic complexes are insoluble in water, but soluble in alcohol, pyridine and other common organic solvents. The vanadyl (IV) complex is insoluble in water or alcohol and other common organic solvents. Elemental analysis, colour and magnetic moment values of the metallic chelates are recorded in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Copper(II) complex: The copper(II) compound corresponds to the composition [CuL₂], where LH = [C₈H₄(OH)CH = N(CH₂)₂OH], with a room temperature (30°) magnetic moment of 1.87 B.M. The magnetic moments of octahedral copper (II) complexes are generally in the range of 1.9–2.0 B.M. and these are independent of temperature^{8,9}. The moments for planar complexes are normally lower than for octahedral complexes ($\mu_{eff} \sim 1.8$ – 1.9 B.M.). As planar stereochemistry may be considered as the limiting case of a tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry, the separation of the interaction terms (*i.e.*, between ground term ²B_{1g} and the components of ²T_{2g} term) is large in square-planar complexes than in the octahedral complexes which possibly explains the lower magnetic moments of square-planar

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TABLE I

Elemental analyses, formulae, colour and magnetic moment values of the complexes of $(C_6H_4(OH)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH)$

Name of the complex and formulae	Colour	Found %				Calcd. %				mag. moment B.M.	
		M	N	Cl	M	N	Cl	M	N		Cl
1. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Copper(II) : $[Cu\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Olive green	16.36	7.07	—	16.24	7.15	—	—	—	—	1.87
2. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Nickel(II) : $[Ni\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Green	14.99	7.01	—	15.18	7.24	—	—	—	—	3.21
3. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Cobalt(III) : $[Co\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2OH \cdot H_2O]$	Chocolate red	14.21	6.95	—	13.96	6.63	—	—	—	—	Diamagnetic
4. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Iron(III) : $[FeCl\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Violet red	14.01	6.45	8.32	13.33	6.67	8.46	—	—	—	5.40
5. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Vanadyl(IV) : $[VO.OH\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}]$	Chocolate	19.71	5.44	—	20.55	5.65	—	—	—	—	1.42
6. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Manganese(II) : $[Mn\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Light brown	14.36	7.12	—	14.60	7.31	—	—	—	—	5.85
7. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Uranyl(VI) : $[UO_2\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Red	38.91	4.50	—	39.80	4.68	—	—	—	—	Diamagnetic
8. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Zinc(II) : $[Zn\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Yellow	16.38	7.02	—	16.63	7.12	—	—	—	—	„
9. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Cadmium(II) : $[Cd\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Yellow	24.78	6.20	—	25.52	6.35	—	—	—	—	„
10. Bis(N-hydroxyethyl-salicylideneiminato)-Palladium(II) : $[Pd\{C_6H_4(O)CH = N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$	Yellow	24.62	6.51	—	24.50	6.44	—	—	—	—	„

complexes^{8,9}. The magnetic moments of perfect tetrahedral complexes are higher than square-planar or octahedral complexes due to spin-orbit coupling and are temperature dependent^{8,9}.

On the basis of the above generalization and on the fact that the measured magnetic moment is 1.87 B.M., the Cu(II) complex under study is believed to have a planar or tetragonally distorted octahedral configuration. The electronic spectra in methanol shows a broad band around 16,810 cm^{-1} , which supports a planar configuration^{10,11} in solution, although a detailed interpretation of the electronic absorption spectra of Cu(II) complexes is somewhat complicated^{12(a,b)}. The second band in this solvent observed around 24,390 cm^{-1} may be associated with intra-ligand or charge-transfer transitions¹³⁻¹⁶. The spectra of the Cu(II) complex in acetonitrile does not show any shift from that of the spectra observed in ethanol or methanol. However, absorption spectra in pyridine show a slight red shift exhibiting one band around 16,600 cm^{-1} and another around 24,110 cm^{-1} . This small shift may be due to the fact that tetragonality of Cu(II) complex in alcohol and in acetonitrile is higher than that in pyridine¹⁷, although the difference is very little. The ligand appears to exhibit bidentate function in this case.

Nickel(II) complex: As stated earlier this complex has recently been studied and reported by Yamada and Coworkers⁵ and was found to be octahedral on the basis of electronic absorption spectra (reported absorption maxima at about 10.7 and 17.0×10^3 cm^{-1}) and magnetic moment value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.95$ B.M.). The compound isolated by us resembles the one described by the above workers in properties, electronic spectra and magnetic moment values. We are, therefore, omitting in the present communication, the description of the same.

Cobalt(III) complexes: An attempt to isolate bis (N-hydroxyethyl salicylideneimino)-cobalt(II) by refluxing requisite amounts of hydrated Cobalt(II) acetate, Schiff base and sodium acetate in ethanol was unsuccessful. Instead, a diamagnetic Co(III) complex was obtained. This is probably due to aerial oxidation of the Co(II) ion during reflux in presence of the basic ligand.

The Cobalt(III) compound is non-conducting in methanol and the elemental analyses corresponds to the composition $[\text{Co(III)L}_2(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, where $\text{LH} = [\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{CH} = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}]$.

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14. G. Basu and S. Basu, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1960, 213, 158.

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The electronic absorption spectrum of the compound in methanol shows the ligand field bands around $26,315\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $15,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$,—which may be assigned to the ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ transitions respectively in O_h field symmetry¹⁸. In pyridine and in acetonitrile solutions two absorption bands are obtained around $\sim 25,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 20,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is consistent with a distorted octahedral structure of Co(III) complex. As the complex is soluble in dil. NH_4OH solution, a spectrum was run in this medium, and this exhibits two bands around $\sim 24,750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 19,630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ —and this again is possibly due to a distorted octahedral configuration of the Co(III) complex in this particular medium.

The infrared spectrum of the complex shows bands at 840 cm^{-1} and 790 cm^{-1} , which might be taken as suggestive of the presence of a co-ordinated water molecule¹⁹. Another strong band around 970 cm^{-1} may probably arise from the $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{—O—H}$ bending vibrations as suggested by Scargill for hydroxo-complexes of ruthenium²⁰. On the basis of above observations, it is suggested that the Schiff base functions as a bidentate ligand in the Co(III) complex, giving rise to a hydroxo-aquo species of distorted octahedral stereochemistry.

Vanadyl (IV) complex: This complex with composition $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{L}]$, where $\text{LH} = [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{OH})\text{CH} = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}]$, is insoluble in water, alcohol and many organic solvents. It is sparingly soluble even in hot pyridine and dimethylsulfoxide. The solution spectrum of the compound could not, therefore, be measured. The room temperature magnetic moment of the complex is 1.42 B.M., which is quite lower than the spin-only value (~ 1.73 B.M.) for d^1 system. This lower magnetic moment value may be compared with the subnormal magnetic moment values (~ 0.77 to 1.55 B.M.) reported by Zelentsov²¹ for vanadyl complexes of N-(O-hydroxyphenyl)-salicylideneimine type of ligands. The d^1 configuration of vanadyl (IV) suggests a spin-coupling phenomenon as it was observed in many copper (II) complexes of tridentate Schiff bases^{22,23}. We could not study the temperature dependence of the magnetic susceptibility of the vanadyl complex, which might throw some light on the mechanism of this magnetic exchange phenomenon^{23,24}. The extreme insolubility of the vanadium (IV) complex under study in common solvents is probably due to the fact that it is actually a dimer (or polymer) with a structure (II a or b) analogous to that of (4-O-hydroxy-phenyl-amino-3-penten-2-ono) copper (II)²⁵. Similar structures for a number of vanadyl complexes of tridentate Schiff bases were proposed by Zelentsov²¹. The exact mechanism for spin-exchange is, however, controversial. Zelentsov suggested the same arising from antiferromagnetic exchange coupling between pairs of vanadyl ions, the

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molecular orbital considerations²⁶ and ESR studies²⁷ also reveal that the direct spin-exchange between two vanadium atoms is not unlikely, and that the spin-coupling via the bridging oxygen atoms may not be the dominant exchange mechanism in vanadium (IV) complexes although suggested for many Cu(II) complexes^{23,28} of tridentate Schiff bases.

FIG (II a)

FIG (II b)

However, the elemental analyses, magnetic moment values and the insolubility of the complex suggest a polymeric distorted octahedral structure, as discussed earlier.

Iron (III) complex: The composition of this compound is given by $[\text{FeClL}_2]$, where $\text{LH} = [\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{CH} = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}]$ and the room temperature (30°) magnetic moment observed for the complex is 5.40 B.M., which is quite lower than the spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) for high-spin d^5 system²⁹. The compound is insoluble in water, but soluble in common organic solvents. It is non-conducting in methanol.

The magnetic behaviour of the complex, indicates that there might be an antiferromagnetic interaction between the iron atoms in the solid state. It seems highly probable that the complex $[\text{FeClL}_2]$ may have a binuclear structure (III) bridging through the phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligands^{30,31}. In such a binuclear structure iron atoms would be six-coordinate and possibly octahedral³² where the Schiff base functions as a bidentate ligand. The molecular weight of the complex in chloroform was found to be 396, whereas the calculated molecular weight for the monomeric complex, $[\text{FeClL}_2]$ is 407. Thus it can be assumed that the present iron (III) complex in solution is monomeric and five-coordinated, which is common for many Fe(III) complexes^{32,33}. So it is obvious that the covalent association in the solid state does not persist in solution. Similar observations are reported by Lewis and coworkers³².

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When the iron complex, $[\text{FeClL}_2]$ was boiled (15 mins.) in pyridine, a dark brown crystalline compound was obtained. This was filtered and washed with little methanol-water mixture and dried in air. From elemental analyses, the empirical formula of the compound was found to be $[\text{FeClL}_2\text{py}]$ and it is non-conducting in nitromethane and shows high-spin magnetic behaviour (5.95 B.M.). This suggests the presence of monomeric units in $[\text{FeClL}_2\text{py}]$ possibly with pyridine as a part of an octahedral complex, which results in the disappearance of the magnetic interaction between iron atoms as noted in the case of the parent compound.

FIG (III)

Manganese (II) complex: The light brown manganous complex $[\text{MnL}_2]$, where $\text{LH} = [\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{CH} = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}]$ has a room temperature (30°) magnetic moment 5.85 B.M. The magnetic moments of both octahedral or tetrahedral Mn(II) complexes should be close to 5.92 B.M., since a ^6S ground state persists in all symmetries of manganese(II) complexes³⁴. The somewhat lower value of the magnetic moment of the present Mn(II) compound may be due to the spin-exchange in the solid states of the complex or to the presence of some Mn(III) species—which may arise due to aerial oxidation as suggested by Holm., *et al.*¹ for such complexes. Similar values of magnetic moments were also obtained for other Mn(II) complexes³⁵⁻³⁷.

The electronic absorption spectrum of the Mn(II) complex under investigation in ethanol exhibits a very strong band around $24,110 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder in the vicinity of $24,120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. They probably originate from charge-transfer phenomenon and the findings are in accord with the octahedral stereochemistry of Mn(II) complexes³⁴. Here also, it is obvious, that the Schiff base functions are tridentate ligand.

Palladium (II) complex: The compound is diamagnetic and elemental analyses suggests the following formula for the compound: $[\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{O})\text{CH} = \text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{OH}\}_2\text{Pd(II)}]$.

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Since Pd(II) greatly favours a square-planar configuration and the various N-alkylsalicylideneiminato-Pd(II) complexes were shown to have a square-planar structure³⁸ the Pd(II) complex, under investigation, is also believed to have a square-planar configuration—where the Schiff base function acts as a bidentate ligand. The solution spectra of Pd(II) complex in methanol and pyridine show little difference indicating that pyridine molecules fail to coordinate with the central Pd(II) ion. This observation is similar to the results obtained by Yamada³⁸ for other planar Pd complexes.

Uranyl (VI), Zinc (II) and Cadmium (II) complexes : All these complexes are diamagnetic as usual and the elemental analyses correspond to the formulation : $[M^{(II)}\{C_6H_4(O)CH=N(CH_2)_2OH\}_2]$, where M = UO_2 (VI), Zn(II) or Cd(II). Zinc (II) and Cadmium(II) complexes are believed to have tetrahedral configuration—the Schiff base behaving as a bidentate ligand as in the case of the copper complex. The Uranyl (VI) complex, probably possesses octahedral stereochemistry as is common with this ion³⁹.

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